

Changes in the humus composition of dark chestnut soils in the post-meliorative period

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The fractional composition of soil humus is an important characteristic of changes occurring in the soil due to agrogenic impact. We studied the post-meliorative state of dark chestnut soil in a rice crop rotation. Twenty years of using the soil for field crops after 38 years of growing rice on it had a drastic effect on the humus content and its qualitative composition.

Before irrigation, the humus content in dark chestnut soil according to P.A. Sadimenko (1966) in the topsoil horizon (0–20), on average, was 3.73%, the humus composition was fulvate-humate. As compared to 1952, a significant increase in the humus content in the topsoil horizon was observed in the rice crop rotation soil by 2002, reaching 4.61%. By 2023, in the soil of the area excluded from rice crop rotation, the humus content decreased by 0.59% in the A1 topsoil horizon, which is 20.8% from the starting point in 2002, and remained practically at the same level in the subsoil horizon. This trend is natural, since an increase in temperature and a decrease in soil moisture always contribute to the mineralization of humus and organic residues. Changes in the humus composition of dark chestnut soil also occurred under the influence of irrigation: in 2002 humus had a humate-fulvate composition according to the classification of D.S. Orlov. Down the profile, the FA content decreased, although the opposite picture is usually observed in dark chestnut soils. This tendency of humus shift towards the increased fulvic acids content is confirmed by literature data for irrigated soils, especially under rice (Gutorova, 2020). In 2023, after 20 years of dry land and cultivation of field crops, a sharp decrease in the proportion of fulvic acids in the humus composition is observed compared to 2002. Although from the period when the soil was irrigated, a higher content of fulvic acids in the upper horizon remains, the FC-1 fraction, as well as calcium fulvates (FC-2), decreases in the composition of fulvic acids to the greatest extent. The humic acid content varies across the profile, reaching its maximum in the middle part of the profile: in 2023 at a depth of 18–30 cm (23.12%), in 2002 – at a depth of 35–45 cm (31.9%). The humic acid content increases slightly in the topsoil horizon. At the same time, in deeper horizons it is significantly lower than it was in 2002. Nevertheless, due to a more significant decrease in the proportion of fulvic acids, the $C_{HA}:C_{FA}$ ratio increases and humus type shifts from fulvate and humate-fulvate to a fulvate-humate type throughout the profile. The share of non-hydrolyzable residue (humins) increased in 2023 compared to 2002 by more than 2 times in topsoil horizon, 1.6 times in the midsoil horizon and 1.4 times in the subsoil.

Thus, the change in hydrothermal and oxidation-reduction regimes contributes to the fixation of humic acids and the formation of strong bonds with the mineral part of the soil. Perhaps, this occurs during the transformation of the mineralogical composition of dark chestnut soil.

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